

Towards an Everyday Political Economy of Labour Migration

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Abstract

This paper introduces the concept of everyday political economy (EPE) to the issue of international labour migration, which has grown in political and economic prominence in the 21st century. The first section of the paper is a literature review regarding existing explanations of labour mobilities from the perspectives of international political economy (IPE), feminist studies, poststructuralist literature, anthropology and human geography, noting their strengths, limitations, and overlaps. Next, EPE is proposed as a way of reconciling the big picture of IPE with the mundane tactics, routines and realities of migrant labourers' everyday lives. In this way, EPE is especially useful for understanding the agency of local actors to embrace, evade, resist and/or be disciplined and subjectivised in relation to powerful state and market structures. Finally, the utility of an EPE analytical lens is illustrated by applying it to the case study of recent Vietnamese migration to, and in, the UK.

Keywords

Labour migration, irregular migration, political economy, migration infrastructures.

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Introduction

For many, migration is a transformative experience, experiencing issues of integration and cultural adaptation, whilst simultaneously creating new identities that are in constant flux. One significant aspect of migration, especially for children of first-generation migrants, is how mate selection and marriage practices are negotiated in the transnational space (Yeung and Mu, 2020). Suarez-Orozco (1991) highlights the notion that migrants have a dual frame of references, whereby, they make constant comparisons between ‘here’ (host country) and ‘there’ (country of origin) and the ‘in-betweenness’ of these impact on identities, creating multiple and *hyphenated* identities (Wolf, 1997). These processes then ultimately shape the decisions of migrants around partner selection and marriage.

International migration is a defining feature of globalised capitalism and has grown in significance during the 21st century, both economically and politically. The total number of international migrants rises each year, creeping up to 3.6% of global population in 2020 according to the IOM (McAuliffe & Triandafyllidou, 2021). The World Economic Forum estimates that global remittance flows in 2022 were worth nearly \$800billion in total (nearly double of that in 2013), with 25 countries dependent on remittances for over 15% of their GDP (Lionell, 2023). Meanwhile the rise of populist politics during the 2010s, rapidly accelerated by the Global Financial Crisis and its aftermath, has been most explicitly manifested in anti-migrant politics – from ‘fortress Europe’ to ‘hostile environment’ to ‘build the wall’. This ramping up of border violence and stripping back of migration rights clearly has negative ramifications for migrants but is by no means reducing the total numbers of people crossing borders in the hope of better work opportunities.

A key question in the world of migration studies is the relationship between structure (migration regimes, borders, market supply-demand etc.) and the agency of ordinary people in migrating, finding work and forging a life for themselves. In this paper I respond to Vargas-Silva’s call for “the production of new conceptual frameworks” (2023, p. 96) in migration studies by arguing that everyday political economy (EPE) provides a useful analytical tool for understanding this relationship. EPE sheds light on the ways in which everyday actors interact with, resist, and are shaped by, multiple (and sometimes contradictory) structural forces within everyday routines and decisions that may often be overlooked but have far-reaching consequences on national and international political economies.

This paper begins with an overview of existing literature in migration studies, focusing on explanations of international labour migration. This means largely overlooking other important topics such as internal migration, forced migration and displacement, diaspora formation, belonging and integration – unless they are directly relevant to issues of labour mobilities. The review will be organised according to the following bodies of literature: of IPE, feminist political economy, governmentality studies, anthropology and human geography. Of course, these fields overlap and many authors have contributed to multiple bodies. While different perspectives provide important insights into the structure-agency relationship, I also identify some of their limitations. Next, I introduce EPE as a way of bringing different perspectives together into a coherent analytical lens. Finally, I briefly apply this to the case study of recent Vietnamese labour migration to the UK, as an example of how to operationalise an EPE lens.

International political economy (IPE): the big picture

International political economy (IPE) concerns the reciprocal relationship between politics and economics in the global system. The fundamental tenet of political economy is that politics and the economy shape each other, even though they may have their own logic and dynamics. Beyond this, however, there are different strands of IPE which approach the topic of labour migration very differently.

Firstly, liberal IPE (also known as the ‘American School’) applies neoclassical rationales of individualist, rational-choice behaviour to both realms of politics and economics (Paul, 2010). A classic example of this is the reduction of migration to simplistic ‘push/pull’ factors, which has been critiqued for “treating migrants as passive pawns” (Bircan et al., 2020, p. 48) – but is still widespread in policy discourse. Another feature which liberal IPE borrows from mainstream economics is a reliance on reductionist, statistical methodology. This is seen in Fitzgerald et al’s claim that “migrants seek to maximize their potential for agency in the political realm when choosing a destination country” (2014, p. 430) based on large-n quantitative data. Mosley and Singer (2015) offer a more nuanced analysis of the roles of states, firms, unions and migrants in affecting political and economic outcomes through trade policies, regulation, FDI and remittances. Ultimately, however, they fall into the same trap of other liberal IPE scholars by providing a relatively ahistoric and overly optimistic account that downplays the power of global structures of inequality.

Conversely, Marxist and other critical IPE strands maintain that “a proper understanding of the politics [in political economy] requires giving special explanatory weight to economic structures and processes” (Gamble, 1995, p. 517). From this perspective, labour migration cannot be understood without reference to historical developments in the global economy and/or world-system (Wallerstein, 1992). This is arguably in contrast with much of the field of migration studies which has “maintained a focus on agency and politics at the expense of the big political economy picture” (Phillips, 2011, p. 3).

Critical IPE perspectives on labour mobilities highlight the massive socio-economic transformations brought about by globalisation from the 1970s onwards, characterised by rapid technological developments, increasing inequality of capital accumulation, increasing mobility of capital, increasing power of transnational corporations and the increasing spatial division of labour (Hobsbawm, 1994). As a result, production processes are no longer confined to national economies but involve outsourcing, subcontracting and relocating of labour-intensive parts of manufacturing to developing countries where labour costs are lower (Piper, 2009). Together with the ‘soft infrastructure’ of neoliberal policy reforms from the 1980s, the mismatch between international capital mobility and partial/restricted labour mobility has skewed the balance of bargaining power decisively away from unions (and national labour regulations) and towards the ‘flexible accumulation’ of capital and firms (Harvey, 1990).

On the one hand, transnational firms’ relocation of production to countries with a surplus of cheap labour massively undermined labour power in industrialised countries (Silver, 2003). On the other hand, global capital mobility creates new demands for a flexible, disposable, reserve army of labour (Savran, 2022) in different locations and at different times – for example, in industries which hire more or less workers depending on fluctuating market demand for the products or services (Lucas & Mansfield, 2010). Migrants are often preferred over local workforces for this reserve labour pool since they have less rights and are therefore more likely to accept precarious working conditions. This facilitates the emergence of what Piore (1979) called the ‘dual labour market’ consisting of a primary segment with stable and (relatively) well-paid jobs and a secondary segment of temporary and poorly

paid (migrant) jobs with little opportunity for progression. There is low inter-segment mobility, because “secondary segment jobs are shunned by native workers out of social status and relative deprivation motives” (de Lange et al., 2021, p. 292). Others describe a ‘bifurcated’ global migration regime system which bestows privileges on ‘high-skill’ professional migrants while condemning low-wage migrants (who constitute the vast majority of global labour migration) to precarity, exploitation, abuse and debt-bondage (Gerard & Bal, 2020).

A critical political economy lens has also been used to explain the relationship between migration and international development, as Massey points out: “international migrants do not come from poor, isolated places that are disconnected from world markets, but from regions and nations that are undergoing rapid change as a result of their incorporation into global trade, information, and production networks” (2009, p. 27). Instead of poverty driving international migration, as is often assumed, it is the dislocations, crises and opportunities brought about by the expansion of capitalist markets which drives migration. For this reason, policies trying to promote ‘development’ in sending countries as a panacea for further migration are misguided and lack evidence (Black, 2023). Nonetheless, the migration-development nexus is complex and reciprocal (de Haas, 2010), as seen by the importance of international remittances – which some countries have come to rely on as a replacement for developing their national economies (Small, 2019, p. 8). Combining the above points on migrant labour exploitation and remittance dependence, Ness (2023) argues that labour migration acts as a form of ‘economic imperialism’ by replicating the same historical relationship of colonial powers extracting value from colonial subjects.

This is by no means an exhaustive list of IPE’s contributions to migration studies. The past few decades have witnessed the further expansion of global (re)production networks, the rise of new sending states promoting migrant exports and the burgeoning of a migration industry led by recruitment networks – all of which has important ramifications for the global political economy and the ‘hyper-precariety’ of labour migrants (Lewis et al., 2014). While a macro structuralist analysis is clearly important, it cannot explain everything; for example, why certain ‘cultures of migration’ (Massey et al., 1993) emerge from a specific country or region and not others. Moreover, the ever-present danger is to ignore or deny the agency of migrants themselves who make their own history, albeit in contexts not of their own choosing. Therefore, we must move beyond IPE to assess the contributions of other approaches.

Gendered political economy: feminist perspectives

The gendered nature of international political, social and trade relations has traditionally been ignored by the study of IPE (Paterson, 1999), and continues to remain a ‘blind spot’ (LeBaron et al., 2020). Of particular relevance to this literature review is the contribution of feminist scholars in revealing the gendered international division of labour, which cross-cuts national boundaries in the ‘age of migration’ (Castles & Miller, 1993) which we inhabit. Feminist analysis highlights the double burden of women’s labour in the productive sphere for markets, involving paid work, and the reproductive sphere, largely involving unpaid work caring for current and future generations within households (Himmelweit, 2000; Hoskyns & Rai, 2007).

Firstly, the unpaid reproductive labour and domestic tasks performed by women all over the world (Kofman, 2014) has facilitated the mass out-migration of men to earn an income without worrying about these duties due to patriarchal norms, leaving women to shoulder the burden of community depletion (Elias, 2020, p. 237). Secondly, the latter half of the twentieth century saw the feminisation of migration and work more broadly, due to “increasing informalisation, casualisation and

precariousness of work” (Piper, 2009, p. 2) associated with the political economy transformations mentioned above. The combination of these two factors leads to a feminisation of poverty (Chant, 2006), with an increased burden placed upon women to be responsible for securing families’ livelihoods and economic survival. Moreover, the female burden of social reproduction is not limited to the home context but is also perpetuated through the sex industry, which expands alongside and is strongly correlated with labour migration, exploitation and trafficking (Andrijasevic, 2021; Marchetti & Salih, 2017).

The feminisation of migration is most clearly seen in the rise of the migrant domestic worker – a role restricted to women from poorer countries who come to clean the homes and care for the children and elderly of households in richer countries. Since many receiving countries do not categorise domestic labour as official work, female migrants are excluded from unions and are particularly vulnerable to exploitation, abuse and being laid off in economic crises or downturns (Elias, 2020). Women from richer countries and/or upper-middle social classes are also complicit in these unequal power relations (Näre, 2013), since they outsource reproductive labour to domestic workers in order to progress in their careers and achieve their own relative empowerment. This occurs within the wider patriarchal context of reproductive labour being devalued and largely unpaid (Bakker & Gill, 2003). Consequently, women are divided by nationality, ethnicity, class and other vectors of inequality which intersectional feminist (and critical race) scholars have stressed the importance of within migration studies (Yeoh & Huang, 1998).

Some migrant labour industries are heavily gendered to reflect patriarchal norms, (i.e. men dominating in construction, fishing etc.) whilst others reinforce these norms by confining women at the bottom of the salary ladder. For example, in Asian electronics factories women were subjugated in the low-paid drudgery of assembly lines for allegedly having more ‘nimble hands’ than men, who were more likely to get managerial/overseer positions (Elson & Pearson, 1981). Nevertheless, gendered migration and work dynamics sometimes combine with other political economic forces to produce unexpected outcomes which do not fit so neatly into reinforcing patriarchy. This will be seen later in my case study whereby Vietnamese migrants to the UK are mostly men, the majority of which work in nail salons – traditionally a very feminised job. Therefore, while feminist contributions to migration studies are undoubtedly crucial, it is helpful to complement them with other conceptual and analytical insights.

Poststructuralist approaches: migrant subjectivities

Inspired by Foucault’s groundbreaking insights on the diffusion of power through governmentality, or the ‘conduct of conducts’, poststructuralist studies have investigated how labour migrants are subjectivised, disciplined and moulded throughout different stages of the migration experience, with the goal of “artificially so arranging things so that people, following their own self-interest, will do as they ought” (D. Scott, 1995, p. 202). This is achieved “by educating desires and configuring habits, aspirations and belief” (Li, 2007, p. 5), especially through “discourses and interpretations purposively constructed by various actors, including the state, media, private sector agents, activists, and migrants themselves” (Hoang, 2020b, p. 74). This provides a further critique of the neoclassical assumption of individual migrants as ‘free agents’, instead pointing to the more subtle, nuanced ways in which subjects are influenced and ‘produced’ by migration regimes, labour markets and brokerage networks (Deshingkar, 2019).

Starting in poorer countries, prospective migrants’ futures and decision-making are informed and shaped by powerful neoliberal narratives such as the ‘will to improve’ (Li, 2007) and the imperative to

be self-responsible and enterprising (M. T. N. Nguyen, 2018). Alongside state labour export initiatives, migrant brokers have emerged as key mediators who may utilise ‘technologies of servitude’ (Rudnycky, 2004) to inculcate aspiring migrants with the necessary skills and submissive (often gendered) attitudes for future work (Liang, 2011). Next, brokerage networks intersect with recruitment agencies and immigration regimes to journey to channel, deskill and position labour migrants in precarious sectors of the destination labour market (Deshingkar, 2019). Laws, trade arrangements and public discourses as well as social networks, ICTs and transport infrastructures all play a role in shaping precarious migrant subjectivities in sending, transit and receiving countries (Sigona et al., 2021). Meanwhile, exclusion from workplace rights (and sometimes human rights) encourages labour docility, discourages politicisation of abuse or exploitation, and engenders new social behaviours when perpetual uncertainty becomes accepted as a ‘way of life’ (Hoang, 2020b).

Such poststructuralist approaches constitute an important contribution to understanding international labour migration. Crucially, governmentality is not (primarily) directly imposed on subjects but is rather mobilised through an assemblage of ‘technologies of rule’ which ‘act at a distance’ (Rose & Miller, 1992) to construct the ideal labour migrant, encouraging the subject to participate in their own subjectification (Tyner, 2004). Most of these studies ascribe a strongly neoliberal bent to the produced migrant subjectivity: self-responsible, resilient, flexible, entrepreneurial and apolitical. For example, Hernandez and Coutin argue that state and development discourses surrounding migrant remittances “contribute to producing the enterprising subjects of neoliberalism” (2006, p. 201), so that the burden of development is placed on migrants rather than the state administering effective policies to provide sustainable work for their populations.

Squire (2016) assesses subjectification to be a path forward beyond the ‘structure vs agency’ debates, noting how subjectivities are not all-powerful but rather messy, incomplete and constantly open to negotiation and even resistance. Moreover, there is a danger of ascribing a theoretical neoliberal governmentality to dominant discourses, without showing how they become distorted, adapted, interpreted, or rejected on the ground (Peck et al., 2018). Therefore, it is important for such studies to remain grounded in observation of everyday behaviour of ‘actually existing neoliberalisms’, ideally through an ethnographic lens (Cotoi, 2011, p. 122).

Anthropology of migration: cultures and infrastructures

One discipline that prides itself on grounding itself on the everyday experience is social anthropology, with its commitment to ethnographic observation. While the traditional anthropological emphasis on one long-term, static field research site has been criticised as inadequate for understanding the contemporary dynamics of transnational mobilities (Marcus, 1995), many have since moved beyond this limitation, for example through multi-site ethnography or narrative approach (Brettell, 2016). In addition to contributions to political economy (Cole & Booth, 2007), feminist (Constable, 1997; Nagy, 1998) and poststructuralist research (Ong, 2006), it is worth mentioning two further interventions of particular relevance to labour mobilities: cultures of migration and migration infrastructures.

Offering another critique of the individualist homo economicus trope, many anthropologists argue that the basic unit of migration analysis should be the household (Cohen & Sirkeci, 2011). It is not primarily the individual, but the household which makes decisions to send a family member off as a migrant labourer, mobilises resources to fund migration journeys, and receives and allocates remittances (Grasmuck & Pessar, 1991, p. 15). Moreover, such mobilities are informed not only by economic but also social and cultural logics, including religious networks (Fesenmyer, 2023) and ritual behaviour

(Chu, 2010). A 'culture of migration' emerges within sending areas where "migration becomes deeply ingrained into the repertoire of people's behaviors, and values associated with migration become part of the community's values" (Massey et al., 1993, pp. 452–453). Such processes "link households and rural communities to global labor markets, flows of goods, and personal demands" (Cohen, 2004, p. 5).

Other anthropologists have enquired into the formation of prominent migrant labour pathways from a different lens, namely, that of migration infrastructures, or "the systematically interlinked technologies, institutions, and actors that facilitate and condition mobility" (Xiang & Lindquist, 2014, p. 124). Highlighting the way in which labour migration is mediated by commercial, regulatory, technological, humanitarian and social dimensions, Xiang and Linquist's seminal work helps explain the durability of migration routes from specific origins. Others have set out to understand 'arrival infrastructures' and networks awaiting migrants at destination countries (Hanhörster & Wessendorf, 2020), including those which push migrants into irregular and exploitative working conditions (Gonzales et al, 2019; Sigona et al., 2021; Piemontese & Sigona, 2024). Such infrastructures not only facilitate but may also restrict, condition and funnel migration, or even become "self-perpetuating and self-serving [which] impedes rather than enhances people's migratory capability." (Xiang & Lindquist, 2014, p. 122).

Human geography: spatial and temporal dimensions

Finally, we turn to the fields of human and labour geography, which are responsible for much of the recent innovation in migration studies. In addition to contributing to the above sections, geographers have drawn attention to the "heightened geographical difference and spatial relationships" wrought by globalisation, as well as "modulated notions of time and temporality" (Ho, 2021, p. 1668). Labour geographers have investigated the condition of precarity as fundamental to the migrant labour experience, which produces alienation, instrumentality and opportunism with "no 'shadow of the future' hanging over their actions, to give them a sense that what they say, do or feel today will have a strong or binding effect on their longer-term relationships" (Standing, 2011, p. 14). Once questions of structure and agency are placed within their spatial and temporal contexts, however, perhaps "not to resist or rework exploitative working conditions may be an act of agency" (Buckley et al., 2018, p. 154) – if it is seen as a necessary 'cost' of securing long-term settlement aspirations (Axelsson et al., 2017).

Fresh developments in the conceptualisation of the 'times of migration' (Cwerner, 2001) are particularly illuminating to the study of international labour mobilities. Transnational families are also 'transtemporal' (Coe, 2016), and ruptures in space or time bear the threat of rupturing and unravelling the very household unit that enabled the migration project (Yeoh et al., 2023). Meanwhile, the merging of public-private boundaries for live-in domestic workers can be seen as "the deprivation of a time-space outside of the workplace" (Gallié et al., 2015, p. 12). Borders have long been identified as "an important mechanism of temporal management" (Mezzadra & Neilson, 2013, p. 134), not only at national demarcations but increasingly within destination countries through the practice of 'everyday bordering' (Yuval-Davis et al., 2018). Griffiths (2021) shows how migrants encounter different paces and rhythms at different stages of their journey including delays, queues, limbo and 'stuckness' on the one hand, followed by 'frenzied time' at other points – all of which cause considerable financial, social, physical and psychological harm (McNevin & Missbach, 2018).

Debt is another crucial aspect of labour migration which is inherently entwined with experiences of temporality, as present costs are bought with future labour (Harker & Kirwan, 2019) – but with present obligations that make us ‘governed by debt’ (Lazzarato, 2012). Datta & Aznar (2019) see transnational migration and debt as defining features of contemporary society; at their intersection, migrants experience ‘weaponized time’ as looming debt gradually pushes them to increasingly precarious work. In this way debt becomes a technology of temporal control, producing “particular kinds of economic subjectivities as waiting time is converted to devalued labour value” (Ho, 2021, p. 1672). Importantly, “debts were never simply financial but also social, moral and emotional relations” (Datta & Aznar, 2019, p. 304) – an observation which is pertinent to the case study of Vietnamese labour migration as will be seen later.

Everyday Political Economy

The preceding, and necessarily brief, literature review has showcased some of the major themes and focal points of the study of international labour migration from different disciplinary and analytical perspectives. Clearly the big picture of global capitalist inequality, as described by IPE, is foundational for our understanding; and even problematic economic concepts of ‘push-pull’ factors can be helpful to an extent. The big picture is necessary, but not sufficient to explain the complexities of household strategies, remittances, gendered experiences, subjectivities, cultures and indebtedness which all influence migrant labour.

What feminist, poststructuralist, anthropological and human geography research all emphasise (in contrast to IPE) is the centrality of the ‘everyday’ as a crucial field of enquiry – not only to observe agency and resistance, but also to understand how structural constraints and oppression operate in real life. In recent years some unorthodox IPE scholars have engaged with these other fields to call for a greater analysis of the ‘subaltern’ and how their “manifold micropolitical struggles intersect with, and alter, macropolitical structures of governance, and vice versa” (Weber, 2010, p. 110). This is where the concept of ‘everyday political economy’ (EPE) has emerged from, and in this section, I introduce the concept’s development before applying an EPE analytical lens to labour migration.

Back in 2007, Hobson and Seabrooke critiqued orthodox IPE’s obsession with hegemony, elites, international trade/financial flows and economic regulatory institutions, with little to say about how the vast majority of the world’s population shape their own lives and beyond. Instead of focusing on who governs, who benefits and how the international system is regulated, an everyday approach asks “who acts and how do their actions constitute and transform the world economy” (Hobson & Seabrooke, 2007, p. 15). Without ignoring “the importance of the dominant, nor... reify[ing] the agency of the weak” (2007, p. 15), it is instructive to focus on the interaction between everyday actors, elites and structures to explore the possibilities and impacts of compliance, evasion, negotiation or resistance (Kerkvliet, 2009). Crucially, power, poverty, empowerment and inequality are all relational in nature (Rumsby, 2023) and EPE seeks to understand these relationships – both concrete (i.e. with local officials) and abstract (i.e. with the market economy).

Elias and Rethel (2016) first coined the term everyday political economy in their analysis of everyday experiences of political contestation, marketisation and economic transformation in Southeast Asia, where international processes became embedded within regionally distinct patterns of social relations and cultural-religious dynamics. Taking a gendered, household-level analysis to expose the ‘violence of everyday life’ (Scheper-Hughes, 1993), Elias et al (2016) identify two distinct analytical aspects of EPE. Firstly, the logic of action or ‘action-centric’ aspect focuses on the ‘weapons of the weak’ (J. C.

Scott, 1987) or tactics (de Certeau, 1984) of non-elites to struggle against, avoid or bargain with state governance in mundane, not overtly political ways, which can nonetheless have important ramifications and force states to reconsider or reverse policy decisions (Kerkvliet, 2005). Secondly, the logics of discipline or ‘agency-centric’ aspect explores the role of discipline and daily routines, aligning to more Foucauldian approaches where the everyday is a site of mundane subjectification. In this way, EPE has the potential to not only recognise and give voice to marginal actors, but also consider “how the conditions of everyday life are themselves produced” (Elias et al., 2016, p. 256).

In my previous research into religious and economic transformations in upland Vietnam, I sought to operationalise EPE as a more generalisable analytical lens for exploring the potential for grassroots empowerment within contexts of poverty and inequality (Rumsby, 2023). Building on Elias and Rethel’s work, I offered two further theoretical contributions: firstly, the “need to consider and even disassociate the multiple [top-down] forces” which everyday actors encounter “including state, market forces and transnational actors, that have distinct agendas and impacts – sometimes overlapping, sometimes conflicting” (2023, p. 15). Secondly, interactions between ordinary people and powerful structures or forces are often mediated by ‘everyday elites’ who act as nodes within broader webs of power relations, often with feet in different camps (Rumsby, 2021a).

The first of these two points can be illustrated in De Lange, Berntsen & De Sena’s (2021) overview of political economy, law and the regulation of migrants’ workplaces. They state that “labour migration is ruled by different forces – state power, contractual freedom, and workplace peculiarities – which can coincide as often as they challenge each other” (2021, p. 291). The three ‘forces’ mentioned are different in nature, but the authors are correct in stating the potentially contradictory effects of such forces in everyday life. For instance, economic imperatives for cheap labour might undermine the state’s power or will to uphold contractual rights that workers should be entitled to. In other occasions, migrants might be able to ‘work the system’ (Berntsen, 2016) and manipulate workplace peculiarities to their advantage under certain conditions, for example if there is a labour shortage in a specific sector. Another example of the contradictory nature of top-down forces is articulated in the ‘migrant paradox’ (Hall, 2021): labour migrants in industrialised countries face conflicting logics of the liberal economy system of austerity governance and the politics of border control, rendering them both economically essential and legally disposable.

Within the world of international labour mobilities, migration recruitment agents and broker networks can be seen as ambivalent ‘everyday elites’ who gatekeep and facilitate migration whilst concurrently “regulating and constructing the ideal worker-subject” (Elias & Louth, 2016, p. 839). At least some of these brokers live in sending regions and are integrated members of the community, while others are (or were) migrants themselves seeking to capitalise on their knowledge by recruiting others (Seng, 2016). Beyond this, everyday elites may include religious and community leaders, people with specialist legal knowledge, or potentially co-ethnic bosses in destination countries who may have been older migrant pioneers. Since their role is to mediate relationships between powerful external forces and local actors, everyday elites can reinforce or challenge the legitimacy of dominant structures, as well as being subject to the moral economy of their communities (J. C. Scott, 1976).

In the following case study, I hope to demonstrate the utility of an EPE analytical lens in bringing together IPE, feminist, Foucauldian and anthropological insights to provide a holistic perspective of international labour migration. In future publications I look forward to integrating the innovations of human and labour geographers to identify the spatial and especially temporal dynamics of EPE, which have to date been relatively neglected within political economy.

Case Study: Vietnamese migration histories

Over the past 75 years Vietnam's migration history has been characterised by distinct cohorts, associated with different political and economic imperatives. The first cohort consists of Vietnamese people who managed to migrate to other countries within the former communist bloc like USSR, East Germany, former Yugoslavia, Czechoslovakia, Poland and so on. Starting from the 1950s, this wave of 'socialist mobilities' (Schwenkel, 2014) usually involved students moving abroad ostensibly to learn new technological and manufacturing skills in order to take back to Vietnam. However, over time many migrants also became involved in the 'black market' (aka market economy), smuggling commodities back to Vietnam. When the USSR disbanded and the Berlin Wall came down, many Vietnamese migrants did not leave but stayed on in these countries and, sooner or later, have become regularised as citizens of these countries in Eastern Europe.

The second cohort started when the US-backed former Republic of Vietnam (or South Vietnam) collapsed in 1975 after Northern Vietnam's communists took over and 'reunified' the country. Southerners were more inclined to see it as an invasion, and many associated to the former regime were rounded up and sent to 're-education camps'. Even more people had their lands and assets confiscated from them, leaving them facing poverty and little prospects. Between 1975 to 1995, approximately 800,000 people took the forbidden and dangerous journey out of Vietnam, usually on small boats – mostly from the South, but also a significant number of ethnic Chinese from the North who were targeted by the revolution as oppressive capitalists due to their powerful business networks. These so-called 'boat people' initially sailed to Hong Kong, Indonesia, Malaysia, the Philippines, Singapore, and Thailand, waiting to be accepted as refugees and eventually relocated to the USA, Canada, Australia, France, West Germany and the UK.

Since mid-1980s economic reforms, Vietnam's economy – and population – has been steadily growing. After the fall of the communist bloc Vietnam had to normalise trading relations with the international community, becoming a member of ASEAN in 1995 and the WTO by 2007. From the late 90s onwards, Vietnam began signing bilateral agreements with other East Asian countries and facilitated a third cohort of low-skill labour migration pathways. The International Labor Organization estimates that there are approximately 400,000 Vietnamese workers abroad (ILO, 2023); the top five destination countries for regular migration are Japan, Taiwan, China, South Korea, Saudi Arabia – mainly in factories or as domestic workers. Official working visas are often sponsored by, and tied to, a specific employer, making Vietnamese labourers highly vulnerable to exploitation and abuse since they are not allowed to simply leave and look for other work (Hoang, 2020a). Nevertheless, the Vietnamese government actively encourages the regularised labour migration route, in order to alleviate youth unemployment in Vietnam and benefit from remittances sent back (Trần & Crinis, 2018).

The fourth cohort is roughly synchronous with the third cohort, but rather consists of the growing number of irregular labour migrants operating outside of the state-regulated avenues over the past 25 years. Over 100,000 Vietnamese nationals cross regional borders to work in China, Laos and Thailand often as seasonal migrants; others have attempted longer irregular journeys into Russia, Eastern Europe, Germany, France Spain and all the way to the UK. The majority of this latter cohort hails from just a few 'backwater' provinces in north-central Vietnam which have been left behind by Vietnam's high economic growth, with little industrial investment and high unemployment rates. These recent migrants are mostly young, male and from working-class or farming backgrounds, with low levels of education (N. N. A. Nguyen, 2017). A disproportionate percentage of them are also Catholic, who are

well represented in sending provinces and often have additional grievances with the Vietnamese state (Keith, 2012), providing further incentives to leave the country.

These migration cohorts overlap and get mixed up within people's complex migration journeys and networks. As a hypothetical example (but based on accounts of my research participants), a Vietnamese man might originally migrate to Malaysia on an official (third wave) working visa. There, he gets a 'taste' for migration but is unsatisfied with the low wages and poor working conditions there. So upon return to Vietnam, he makes a new plan to migrate to Europe irregularly (fourth wave) in the hopes of a better salary. For a while, he gets stuck in Czech Republic, working without a visa in a restaurant for a former Czech citizen of Vietnamese origin (first wave). From there, he tries his luck migrating further west to the UK, and ends up working in a nail salon for a former refugee – now part of the Vietnamese UK diaspora (second wave).

EPE of Vietnamese migration to the UK

What would an EPE approach to recent Vietnamese labour migration look like? For now, I briefly operationalise an EPE analytical lens in both the sending region of North-central Vietnam and the migrant-receiving destination of the UK. In both contexts I identify the political and socio-economic position of labour migrants (or prospective migrants), the prominent forces and structures attempting to govern, influence and pressurise them, and the evidence of local agency in everyday life. There are distinct local dynamics in Vietnam and the UK which affect relationships between local actors and powerful forces, but the two contexts are also fundamentally connected via movements of people and finance, which mutually influence each other over time. The migration journey itself could be conceived as a third context for analysis, but there is not the space to do justice to its complexities here.

North-central Vietnam

Vietnam's consistently high levels of economic growth, for decades now, have been highly geographically concentrated in two industrial regions in and around the major cities of Hanoi (North) and Ho Chi Minh City (South). This has facilitated the emergence of a burgeoning Vietnamese middle class with disposable income, at the same time as dramatically increasing economic inequality and inflation (Rigg, 2016). Concurrently, the Vietnamese government actively promotes a 'socialization' (a.k.a. privatisation) agenda whereby "people should rely on their own resources for their well-being while actively contributing to social causes... except for the neediest and most incapacitated, deemed to be failing subjects" (M. T. N. Nguyen & Chen, 2017, p. 235). This combines with the pernicious 'will to improve' (Li, 2007) to instil a desperation for poorer Vietnamese subjects to 'move up the social ladder' (vươn lên) by any means possible (Rumsby, 2021b).

International migration is seen as a panacea, both by local people who want to participate in the middle-class consumer culture which they see advertised so much on TV and social media, and also by the government as a way of resolving high unemployment rates and thereby ameliorate social discontent (A. Nguyen, 2023). Local officials actively promote labour emigration and praise districts with the highest national rates of emigration in the North-central provinces of Nghệ An and Hà Tĩnh. Migrant broker agencies have flourished with the demand, constructing migration infrastructures to facilitate migration via both official and unofficial routes. Brokers often work in direct partnership with money lenders and mafia-esque 'black market' loan sharks to finance the often-exorbitant brokerage fees (Hoang, 2020a).

This combination of economic inequality and ‘socialization’ governmentality has exerted a powerful influence over the people of North-central Vietnam, and the ‘will to improve’ has been fully internalized. It has motivated migrants to endure considerable hardship and even risk death through irregular border crossings, rather than face the ‘social death’ (Longazel & Hallett, 2021) of being stuck in a dead-end backwater with no prospects of rising up the social ladder or investing in their children’s education. After the shocking Essex-39 tragedy, when 39 Vietnamese people were found dead in the back of a lorry attempting to cross the English Channel tunnel, the UK embassy cooperated with Vietnamese authorities to launch a PR campaign in North-central Vietnam warning about the dangers of irregular migration and urging people to reconsider (Gavard, 2020). However, the campaign failed, and subsequent migration rates did not drop at all; indeed, research participants inform me that many more migrants die en route but are never reported in the media.

This ‘stubbornness’, ability to endure hardship and even recklessness has come to be identified as (masculine) cultural attributes of the North-central Vietnamese people and can arguably be seen as a display of agency in the face of considerable structural violence. Beyond this, local migrant brokers and money lenders have had little trouble operating outside legal parameters to facilitate irregular migration, co-opting local officials in the process. This exposes the contradictory logics within the state of enforcing migration law on the one hand (or at least being seen to make an effort by the UK and other stakeholders), and the economic imperative of benefitting from migrant remittances which in practice overrides concerns of legality or labour exploitation. Nevertheless, although remittances align with state objectives, the construction of fancy new houses and increasing consumption, paid for by international currency, are also evidence of the everyday agency of labour migrants. Tellingly, the three North-central provinces of Nghệ An, Hà Tĩnh and Thanh Hóa are in the top 10 (out of 58) provinces for both highest number of poor households and highest numbers of cars purchased (Tran, 2022).

These dynamics are illustrated in the below EPE framework (Figure 1), which attempts to capture the relationships and interactions between prospective migrants and state and market structures in North-central Vietnam. Solid arrows represent the pressures and influences exerted by powerful external structures on local actors, while the dotted lines represent the latter’s reactions and tactics in response. This illuminates the multiple, sometimes contradictory forces which poor rural and working-class people face and navigate in everyday life, which elicit different responses. Of course, the reality is more nuanced than the framework suggests, since ‘local actors’ are further differentiated by gender, location (urban vs rural), religion and connections with local authorities – all of which affect their responses to external pressures. The framework could also be expanded by adding lines to highlight the unequal and sometimes fractious relationships between external forces.

Figure 1: EPE framework of North-central Vietnam sending context.

In the UK

Upon arrival to the UK, irregular Vietnamese migrants immediately face the ‘hostile environment’ of the UK’s Home Office, and most opt to claim asylum which allows them to stay (but not work) while their case is reviewed – a process which may take several years. During this time, the menial asylum allowance provided is not enough to live on, let alone repay the immense debts incurred back in Vietnam which are daily accruing interest. This invariably pushes migrants to seek informal work from Vietnamese business owners, some of whom are willing to turn a blind eye to their lack of legal permission to work. Nail salon bosses, many of whom are older migrants but now with the legal right to work, are likely to frame this in terms of ethnic solidarity and providing a lifeline for newcomers. This narrative is not purely rhetorical: during the pandemic there was evidence of bosses showing considerable hospitality and providing accommodation to destitute migrants who could not work and were ineligible for the furlough scheme.

Nevertheless, this ‘stretched solidarity’ (Keles et al., 2019) rubs up directly with the inherent tensions between workers and owners of the means of production. It is common for migrants to work long hours for well below minimum wage, leading to the Vietnamese nail salon industry being targeted by the government as sites of ‘modern slavery’ (Barber et al., 2023). This language is problematic and fundamentally misunderstands the nature of work relationships at play. For one, migrants are not indebted to bosses or ‘trafficking gangsters’, but rather to family, friends and loan sharks back in Vietnam – this results in a kind of ‘self-exploitation’ (Lainez, 2019) which many unscrupulous brokers and bosses take advantage of. On the other hand, migrants are more often than not willing to work under such conditions, knowing that they can still earn more than they used to back in Vietnam, and start to save and repaying debts if they live in cheap shared accommodation without spending much on themselves.

Furthermore, mobile workers in precarious environments can exert their negotiative agency by walking out on a job without notice (since they have no work contract) to take up a slightly better paid opportunity at a different salon, or if the existing boss is abusive. Bosses regularly complain about this

behaviour, but it has become an incentive for treating their workers with at least some basic shared standards in the moral economy of the nail salon. Unfortunately, these standards do not include a healthy working environment, with both nail salon bosses and workers spending far too long inhaling harmful fumes from the chemical products and complaining about skin reactions, as well as aching necks and shoulders from the manual labour involved. Those who secure legal right to work have more bargaining power than irregular workers and can also negotiate better wages, but most struggle to find better work outside the nail salon industry due to limited English language skills.

At a wider level, the agency of the Vietnamese migrant community is clearly seen in the way it has carved out a significant niche in the UK cosmetics industry. Admittedly, this has been through the 'McDonaldisation' (Eckstein & Nguyen, 2011) of the nail salon, stripping back the niceties of a formerly luxury service to provide a cheap, fast and bare-bones service instead; this equates to reduced revenues and more intensive working conditions. Nevertheless, by cutting the price of a manicure in half, the Vietnamese business model has opened up the market to a much wider customer base who can now afford to get their nails done every month instead of once or twice a year. Therefore, both the supply and demand has increased significantly, and Vietnamese-run nail salons have expanded to every town and city across the UK. Not inconsequentially, this expansion has bucked the broader trend of inner-city retail shops struggling and closing down in recent years (Jones & Ram, 2011), so Vietnamese nail salons are in fact mitigating the 'death of the British high street'.

In this second EPE framework of migrant labour in the UK (see below), I split the Vietnamese community into two analytical groups, based on the distinction of business owner and worker which fundamentally shapes their interactions with state and market forces. This generalisation should not obscure the reality that the two groups are somewhat porous, as workers can (and do) become bosses over time and some external pressures such as the cost-of-living crisis affect both groups. Again, we see a contradiction between the UK Home Office's attempts to clamp down on informal economy and the market's demand for cheap labour. Nail salon owners find themselves squeezed between competition with ever-increasing numbers of newly opened salons on the one hand, and diminishing supply of customers cutting back on luxury services in the UK economy's stagnation and falling real wages. This pressurises bosses towards informal economic practices such as not declaring revenues to avoid paying tax and/or driving down wages for workers. In turn, migrant workers react differently depending on their own legal status, with irregular workers generally more likely to accept exploitative conditions.

Figure 2: EPE framework of Vietnamese migrant labour in the UK.

Conclusion

This paper has covered a lot of ground in the attempt to understand and bring together different perspectives regarding international labour migration. International Political Economy has made important contributions about the structures of global economic inequality and border governance which create the demand for low-paid migrant labour. Feminist scholars reveal the gendered nature of labour migration and how this intersects with other vectors of inequality to place additional burdens and vulnerabilities on women. Foucauldian studies have elucidated the ways in which migrant subjects are influenced, pressurised, encouraged and ‘produced’ by indirect technologies of rule at various stages of the migration process. Anthropologists make further contributions on the nature of cultures of labour migration and the mechanics of migration infrastructures. In addition, human geographers have shed light on the spatial and temporal inequalities involved in precarious labour, border control and debt-fuelled-migration.

I have argued that Everyday Political Economy is a useful and flexible analytical tool for merging many of the above insights into a coherent framework. In particular, it offers a way of reconciling the ‘big picture’ of international structures and politico-economic forces with the mundane, everyday space which labour migrants inhabit and exert their agency. By combining the ‘actor-centric’ logic of people’s tactics to embrace, evade or resist external forces with the ‘agency-centric’ processes of discipline and subjectivities in everyday routines, EPE offers a nuanced analysis of migrant agency in relation to dominant structures. Finally, I operationalised this framework by applying it to the case of recent Vietnamese migration to the UK which emphasised the marginalised socio-economic position of prospective and current migrants, the variegated and sometimes mutually conflicting influences of external state and market forces, and the agency of local actors in their differing respective responses. While this case study analysis is admittedly brief and simplified, I hope that it can inspire readers to consider the benefits of applying an EPE analytical lens to different contexts of labour migration.

Bibliography

- Andrijasevic, R. (2021). Forced labour in supply chains: Rolling back the debate on gender, migration and sexual commerce. *European Journal of Women's Studies*, 28(4), 410–424. <https://doi.org/10.1177/13505068211020791>
- Axelsson, L., Malmberg, B., & Zhang, Q. (2017). On waiting, work-time and imagined futures: Theorising temporal precariousness among Chinese chefs in Swedens restaurant industry. *Geoforum*. *Geoforum*, 78, 169–178.
- Bakker, I., & Gill, S. (2003). *Power, Production and Social Reproduction: Human In/security in the Global Political Economy*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Barber, T., Nguyen, H., & Nguyen, P. Van. (2023). Integration beyond 'modern slavery'? Vietnamese experiences of agency and precarity in the UK immigration system. *Journal of Immigration, Asylum and Nationality Law*, 37(1).
- Berntsen, L. (2016). Reworking labour practices: on the agency of unorganized mobile migrant construction workers. *Work, Employment and Society*, 30(3), 472–488. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0950017015617687>
- Bircan, T., Purkayastha, D., Ahmad-Yar, A. W., Lotter, K., Iakono, C. D., Göler, D., Stanek, M., & Yilmaz, S. (2020). Gaps in Migration Research: Review of Migration Theories and the Quality and Compatibility of Migration Data on the National and International Level.
- Black, R. (2023). Migration Choices in the Context of Development. In L. Lessard-Phillips, A. Papoutsis, N. Sigona, & P. Ziss (Eds.), *Migration, Displacement and Diversity: the IRiS Anthology* (pp. 167–171). Oxford Publishing Services.
- Brettell, C. B. (2016). Perspectives on Migration Theory—Anthropology. In M. J. White (Ed.), *International Handbook of Migration and Population Distribution* (pp. 41–67). Springer Netherlands. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-017-7282-2_4
- Buckley, M., McPhee, S., & Rogaly, B. (2018). Labour geographies on the move: migration, migrant status and work in the 21st century. *Geoforum*, 78, 153–158.
- Castles, S., & Miller, M. J. (1993). *The Age of Migration: International Population Movements in the Modern World*. Macmillan.
- Chant, S. (2006). Re-thinking the “Feminization of Poverty” in Relation to Aggregate Gender Indices. *Journal of Human Development*, 7(2), 201–220. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14649880600768538>
- Chu, J. Y. (2010). *Transnational Mobility and the Politics of Destination in China*. Duke University Press. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctv111jj1s>
- Coe, C. (2016). Orchestrating Care in Time: Ghanaian Migrant Women, Family, and Reciprocity. *American Anthropologist*, 118(1), 37–48. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/aman.12446>
- Cohen, J. H. (2004). *The Culture of Migration in Southern Mexico*. University of Texas Press. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/10.7560/705708>
- Cohen, J. H., & Sirkeci, I. (2011). *The Global Nature of Contemporary Mobility*. University of Texas Press. <https://doi.org/10.7560/726840>
- Cole, J. E., & Booth, S. S. (2007). *Dirty work: Immigrants in domestic service, agriculture, and prostitution in Sicily*. Lexington Books.

- Constable, N. (1997). Sexuality and Discipline among Filipina Domestic Workers in Hong Kong. *American Ethnologist*, 24(3), 539–558. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1525/ae.1997.24.3.539>
- Cotoi, C. (2011). Neoliberalism: a Foucauldian Perspective. *International Review of Social Science*, 1(2), 109–124.
- Cwerner, S. B. (2001). The Times of Migration. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 27(1), 7–36. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13691830125283>
- Datta, K., & Aznar, C. (2019). The space-times of migration and debt: Re-positioning migrants' debt and credit practices and institutions in, and through, London. *Geoforum*, 98, 300–308. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2018.07.009>
- de Certeau, M. (1984). *The Practice of Everyday Life*. University of California Press.
- de Haas, H. (2010). Migration and Development: A Theoretical Perspective. *The International Migration Review*, 44(1), 227–264. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/20681751>
- de Lange, T., Berntsen, L., & de Sena, P. (2021). Political economy, law and the regulation of migrants' workplaces. In *Handbook on the Governance and Politics of Migration* (pp. 291–303). Edward Elgar.
- Deshingkar, P. (2019). The making and unmaking of precarious, ideal subjects – migration brokerage in the Global South. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 45(14), 2638–2654.
- Eckstein, S., & Nguyen, T.-N. (2011). The Making and Transnationalization of an Ethnic Niche: Vietnamese Manicurists. *The International Migration Review*, 45(3), 639–674.
- Elias, J. (2020). The Gendered Political Economy of Southeast Asian Development. In T. Carroll, S. Hameiri, & L. Jones (Eds.), *The Political Economy of Southeast Asia: Politics and Uneven Development under Hyperglobalisation* (pp. 227–248). Palgrave Macmillan.
- Elias, J., & Louth, J. (2016). Producing Migrant Domestic Work: Exploring the Everyday Political Economy of Malaysia's 'Maid Shortage'. *Globalizations*, 13(6), 830–845. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14747731.2016.1155340>
- Elias, J., & Rethel, L. (2016). *The Everyday Political Economy of Southeast Asia*. Cambridge University Press.
- Elias, J., Rethel, L., Hobson, J. M., & Seabrooke, L. (2016). Everyday International Political Economy Meets the Everyday Political Economy of Southeast Asia. In J. Elias & L. Rethel (Eds.), *The Everyday Political Economy of Southeast Asia* (pp. 239–260). Cambridge University Press.
- Elson, D., & Pearson, R. (1981). 'Nimble Fingers Make Cheap Workers': An Analysis of Women's Employment in Third World Export Manufacturing. *Feminist Review*, 7, 87–107. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1394761>
- Fesenmyer, L. (2023). *Relative Distance: Kinship, Migration, and Christianity between Kenya and the United Kingdom*. In *The International African Library*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/DOI:10.1017/9781009335096>
- Fitzgerald, J., Leblang, D., & Teets, J. C. (2014). Defying the Law of Gravity: The Political Economy of International Migration. *World Politics*, 66(3), 406–445. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/24577524>
- Gallié, M., Galerand, E., & Gobeil, J. O. (2015). *Domestic Labour and Exploitation: The Case of Live-In Caregiver Program in Canada* (MigrantWorkersRights Global).

- Gamble, A. (1995). The New Political Economy. *Political Studies*, 43(3), 516–530. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9248.1995.tb00320.x>
- Gavard, V. (2020). A year after Essex lorry deaths, UK-funded ads won't stop Vietnamese migrants risking their lives. *The Conversation*. <https://theconversation.com/a-year-after-essex-lorry-deaths-uk-funded-ads-wont-stop-vietnamese-migrants-risking-their-lives-148653>
- Gerard, K., & Bal, C. S. (2020). Labour Migration in Southeast Asia: The Political Economy of Poor and Uneven Governance. In T. Carroll, S. Hameiri, & L. Jones (Eds.), *The Political Economy of Southeast Asia: Politics and Uneven Development under Hyperglobalisation* (pp. 249–270). Palgrave Macmillan.
- Grasmuck, S., & Pessar, P. P. (1991). *Between Two Islands: Dominican International Migration*. University of California.
- Gonzales, R.G., Sigona, N., Franco, M. Papoutsis, A. (2019) *Undocumented migration*. Cambridge: Polity
- Griffiths, M. (2021). Interrogating time and temporality in migration governance. In E. Carmel, K. Lenner, & R. Paul (Eds.), *Handbook on the Governance and Politics of Migration* (pp. 316–328). Edward Elgar Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781788117234.00036>
- Hall, S. M. (2021). *The Migrant's Paradox: Street Livelihoods and Marginal Citizenship in Britain*. University of Minnesota Press. <https://doi.org/10.5749/j.ctv1g809h9>
- Hanhörster, H., & Wessendorf, S. (2020). The Role of Arrival Areas for Migrant Integration and Resource Access. *Urban Planning*, 5(3), 1–10.
- Harker, C., & Kirwan, S. (2019). Introduction: Geographies of Debt and Indebtedness. *Geoforum*, 100, 236–238. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2019.02.021>
- Harvey, D. (1990). Between Space and Time: Reflections on the Geographical Imagination. *Annals of the Association of American Geographers*, 80(3), 418–434. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8306.1990.tb00305.x>
- Hernandez, E., & Coutin, S. B. (2006). Remitting subjects: migrants, money and states. *Economy and Society*, 35(2), 185–208.
- Himmelweit, S. (2000). *Inside the Household: From Labour to Care*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Ho, E. L.-E. (2021). Social geography I: Time and temporality. *Progress in Human Geography*, 45(6), 1668–1677. <https://doi.org/10.1177/03091325211009304>
- Hoang, L. A. (2020a). Debt and (un)freedoms: The case of transnational labour migration from Vietnam. *Geoforum*, 116, 33–41. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2020.08.001>
- Hoang, L. A. (2020b). *Vietnamese Migrants in Russia: Mobility in Times of Uncertainty*. Amsterdam University Press.
- Hobsbawm, E. J. (1994). *Age of extremes: the short twentieth century, 1914-1991*. Viking Penguin.
- Hobson, J. M., & Seabrooke, L. (2007). *Everyday Politics of the World Economy*. Cambridge University Press.
- Hoskyns, C., & Rai, S. M. (2007). Recasting the Global Political Economy: Counting Women's Unpaid Work. *New Political Economy*, 12(3), 297–317. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13563460701485268>
- ILO. (2023). Labour migration in Viet Nam. <https://www.ilo.org/hanoi/Areasofwork/labour-migration/lang--en/index.htm>

- Jones, T., & Ram, M. (2011). *Ethnic Entrepreneurs and Urban Regeneration*. In A. Southern (Ed.), *Enterprise, Deprivation and Social Exclusion: The Role of Small Business in Addressing Social and Economic Inequalities*. Routledge.
- Keith, C. (2012). *Catholic Vietnam: A Church from Empire to Nation*. University of California Press.
- Keles, J. Y., Markova, E., & Fatah, R. (2019). Migrants with insecure legal status and access to work: the role of ethnic solidarity networks. *Equality, Diversity and Inclusion*, ISSN 2040-7149.
- Kerkvliet, B. J. (2005). *The power of everyday politics: how Vietnamese peasants transformed national policy*. Cornell University Press.
- Kerkvliet, B. J. (2009). Everyday politics in peasant societies (and ours). *Journal of Peasant Studies*, 36(1), 227–243. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03066150902820487>
- Kofman, E. (2014). Gendered migrations, social reproduction and the household in Europe. *Dialectical Anthropology*, 38(1), 79–94. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/43895201>
- Lainez, N. (2019). The debts of undocumented Vietnamese in Europe. *OpenDemocracy*. <https://www.opendemocracy.net/en/beyond-trafficking-and-slavery/debts-undocumented-vietnamese-migrants-europe/>
- Lazzarato, M. (2012). *Governing by Debt*. Semiotext(e).
- LeBaron, G., Mügge, D., Best, J., & Hay, C. (2020). Blind spots in IPE: marginalized perspectives and neglected trends in contemporary capitalism. *Review of International Political Economy*, 28(2), 283–294. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09692290.2020.1830835>
- Lewis, H., Dwyer, P., Hodgkinson, S., & Waite, L. (2014). Hyper-precarious lives: Migrants, work and forced labour in the Global North. *Progress in Human Geography*, 39(5), 580–600. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0309132514548303>
- Li, T. M. (2007). *The Will to Improve: Governmentality, Development, and the Practice of Politics*. Duke University Press.
- Liang, L.-F. (2011). The Making of an ‘Ideal’ Live-In Migrant Care Worker : Recruiting, Training, Matching and Disciplining. *Ethnic and Racial Studies*, 34, 1815–1834. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01419870.2011.554571>
- Lionell, R. (2023). Animated chart: Remittance flows and GDP impact by country. <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2023/01/chart-remittance-flows-impact-gdp-country/>
- Longazel, J., & Hallett, M. C. (2021). *Migration and Mortality: Social Death, Dispossession, and Survival in the Americas*. Temple University Press.
- Lucas, R., & Mansfield, S. (2010). The Use of Migrant Labour in the Hospitality Sector: Current and Future Implications. In M. Ruhs & B. Anderson (Eds.), *Who Needs Migrant Workers? Labour shortages, immigration, and public policy* (pp. 159–192). Oxford Academic Press.
- Marchetti, S., & Salih, R. (2017). Policing gender mobilities: interrogating the ‘feminisation of migration’ to Europe. *International Review of Sociology*, 27(1), 6–24. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03906701.2017.1303966>
- Marcus, G. E. (1995). Ethnography in/of the World System: The Emergence of Multi-Sited Ethnography. *Annual Review of Anthropology*, 24, 95–117. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/2155931>

- Massey, D. S. (2009). The Political Economy of Migration in an Era of Globalization. In *International Migration and Human Rights* (pp. 25–43). University of California Press. <https://doi.org/doi:10.1525/9780520942578-003>
- Massey, D. S., Arango, J., Hugo, G., Kouaouci, A., Pellegrino, A., & Taylor, J. E. (1993). Theories of International Migration: A Review and Appraisal. *Population and Development Review*, 19(3), 431–466. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2938462>
- McAuliffe, M., & Triandafyllidou, A. (2021). *International Organization for Migration: World Migration Report 2022*.
- McNevin, A., & Missbach, A. (2018). Hospitality as a Horizon of Aspiration (or, What the International Refugee Regime Can Learn from Acehnese Fishermen). *Journal of Refugee Studies*, 31(3), 292–313. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jrs/fey014>
- Mezzadra, S., & Neilson, B. (2013). *Border as Method, or, the Multiplication of Labor*. Duke University Press. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctv1131cvw>
- Mosley, L., & Singer, D. A. (2015). Migration, Labor, and the International Political Economy. *Annual Review of Political Science*, 18(1), 283–301. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-polisci-020614-094809>
- Nagy, S. (1998). “This Time I Think I’ll Try a Filipina”: Global and Local Influences on Relations Between Foreign Household Workers and Their Employers in Doha, Qatar. *City & Society*, 10(1), 83–103. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1525/city.1998.10.1.83>
- Näre, L. (2013). Migrancy, Gender and Social Class in Domestic Labour and Social Care in Italy: An Intersectional Analysis of Demand. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 39(4), 601–623. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369183X.2013.745238>
- Ness, I. (2023). *Migration as Economic Imperialism: How International Labour Mobility Undermines Economic Development in Poor Countries*. Polity.
- Nguyen, A. (2023). *Labour Export – A Life-Changing Dream for Vietnamese Workers*. ASEAN-Australia Strategic Youth Partnership. <https://aasyp.org/2023/06/11/labour-export-a-life-changing-dream-for-vietnamese-workers/>
- Nguyen, M. T. N. (2018). Vietnam’s ‘socialization’ policy and the moral subject in a privatizing economy. *Economy and Society*, 47(4), 627–647. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03085147.2018.1544397>
- Nguyen, M. T. N., & Chen, M. (2017). The Caring State? On Rural Welfare Governance in Post-reform Vietnam and China. *Ethics and Social Welfare*, 11(3), 230–247.
- Nguyen, N. N. A. (2017). *Social Networks along the Migration Cycle between Vietnam and Korea: Opportunities or Obstacles for Temporary Labour Migrants?* The University of Sydney.
- Ong, A. (2006). *Neoliberalism as Exception: Mutations in Citizenship and Sovereignty*. Duke University Press.
- Paterson, R. (1999). Towards a feminist international political economy. *Melbourne Journal of Politics*, 26, 1+.
<https://link.gale.com/apps/doc/A80056873/AONE?u=anon~e410d96b&sid=googleScholar&xid=d17ae955>

- Paul, D. E. (2010). Liberal Perspectives on the Global Political Economy. In R. A. Denmark & R. Marlin-Bennett (Eds.), *The International Studies Encyclopedia*. Wiley-Blackwell. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acref/9780191842665.013.0260>
- Peck, J., Brenner, N., & Theodore, N. (2018). Actually Existing Neoliberalism. In D. Cahill, M. Cooper, & M. Konings (Eds.), *The SAGE handbook of neoliberalism* (pp. 3–15). SAGE Publications.
- Phillips, N. (2011). *Migration in the Global Political Economy*. Lynne Rienner Publishers.
- Piemontese, S. and Sigona, N. (2024) *The legal and policy infrastructure of irregularity: United Kingdom*. I-CLAIM. DOI: <https://zenodo.org/records/10977054>
- Piore, M. J. (1979). *Birds of Passage: Migrant Labor in Industrial Societies*. Cambridge University Press.
- Piper, N. (2009). *The Gendered Political Economy of Migration* (IMDS Working Paper Series).
- Rigg, J. (2016). *Challenging Southeast Asian Development: The Shadows of Success*. Routledge.
- Rose, N., & Miller, P. (1992). Political Power beyond the State: Problematics of Government. *The British Journal of Sociology*, 43(2), 173–205. <https://doi.org/10.2307/591464>
- Rudnyckij, D. (2004). Technologies of Servitude: Governmentality and Indonesian Transnational Labor Migration. *Anthropological Quarterly*, 77(3), 407–434. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/3318228>
- Rumsby, S. (2021a). Hmong Christian elites as political and development brokers: competition, cooperation and mimesis in Vietnam’s highlands. *Social Anthropology*, 29(3), 701–717.
- Rumsby, S. (2021b). Hmong Christianisation, the will to improve and the question of neoliberalism in Vietnam’s highlands. *European Journal of East Asian Studies*.
- Rumsby, S. (2023). *Development in Spirit: Religious Transformation and Everyday Politics in Vietnam’s Highlands*. University of Wisconsin Press.
- Savran, S. (2022). The Political Economy of Migration. In E. Balkan & Z. K. Tonak (Eds.), *Refugees on the Move: Crisis and Response in Turkey and Europe* (pp. 13–37). Berghahn.
- Scheper-Hughes, N. (1993). *Death without Weeping: The Violence of Everyday Life in Brazil*. University of California Press.
- Schwenkel, C. (2014). Rethinking Asian Mobilities: Socialist Migration and Post-Socialist Repatriation of Vietnamese Contract Workers in East Germany. *Critical Asian Studies*, 46(2), 235–258.
- Scott, D. (1995). Colonial Governmentality. *Social Text*, 43, 202–203.
- Scott, J. C. (1976). *The Moral Economy of the Peasant: Rebellion and Subsistence in Southeast Asia*. Yale University Press.
- Scott, J. C. (1987). *Weapons of the Weak: Everyday Forms of Peasant Resistance*. Yale University Press.
- Seng, S. (2016). Unseen: Undocumented Cambodian Migrant Workers in Thailand. In K. Um & S. Gaspar (Eds.), *Southeast Asian Migration: People on the Move in Search of Work, Refuge and Belonging* (pp. 159–179). Sussex University Press.
- Sigona, N., Kato, J., & Kuznetsova, I. (2021a). Migration infrastructures and the production of migrants’ irregularity in Japan and the United Kingdom. *Comparative Migration Studies*, 9(1), 31. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40878-021-00242-4>

- Silver, B. J. (2003). *Forces of Labor: Workers' Movements and Globalization Since 1870*. In *Cambridge Studies in Comparative Politics*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/DOI:10.1017/CBO9780511615702>
- Small, I. (2019). *Currencies of Imagination: Channeling Money and Chasing Mobility in Vietnam*. Cornell University Press.
- Squire, V. (2016). Unauthorised migration beyond structure/agency? Acts, interventions, effects. *Politics*, 37(3), 254–272. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0263395716679674>
- Standing, G. (2011). *The Precariat: The New Dangerous Class*. Bloomsbury Academic.
- Trần, A. N., & Crinis, V. (2018). Migrant Labor and State Power: Vietnamese Workers in Malaysia and Vietnam. *Journal of Vietnamese Studies*, 13(2), 27–73.
- Tran, T. (2022). People in poor provinces are buying more cars. <https://vietnamnet.vn/en/people-in-poor-provinces-are-buying-more-cars-822656.html>
- Tyner, J. A. (2004). *Made in the Philippines: Gendered Discourses and the Making of Migrants*. Routledge.
- Vargas-Silva, C. (2023). Directions of and Developments in the Field of Migration Studies. In L. Lessard-Phillips, A. Papoutsi, N. Sigona, & P. Ziss (Eds.), *Migration, Displacement and Diversity: the IRIS Anthology* (pp. 96–99). Oxford Publishing Services.
- Wallerstein, I. (1992). The West, Capitalism, and the Modern World-System. *Review* (Fernand Braudel Center), 15(4), 561–619. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/40241239>
- Weber, H. (2010). Politics of Global Social Relations: Organising 'Everyday Lived Experiences' of Development and Destitution. *Australian Journal of International Affairs*, 64(1), 105–122.
- Xiang, B., & Lindquist, J. (2014). Migration Infrastructure. *International Migration Review*, 48(1_suppl), 122–148. <https://doi.org/10.1111/imre.12141>
- Yeoh, B. S. A., & Huang, S. (1998). Negotiating Public Space: Strategies and Styles of Migrant Female Domestic Workers in Singapore. *Urban Studies*, 35(3), 583–602. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0042098984925>
- Yeoh, B. S. A., Lam, T., Somaiah, B. C., & Acedera, K. A. F. (2023). The critical temporalities of serial migration and family social reproduction in Southeast Asia. *Time & Society*, 32(4), 411–433. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0961463X231164473>
- Yuval-Davis, N., Wemyss, G., & Cassidy, K. (2018). Everyday Bordering, Belonging and the Reorientation of British Immigration Legislation. *Sociology*, 52(2), 228–244.